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Silencing of DDX family helicases in liver metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer.

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The liver is the most common site of metastasis in patients with colorectal cancer (1-5). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (10, 11) to measure total transcription in the liver metastases of humans with colorectal cancer. We describe a set of genes from the DEAD-box (DDX) helicase that are differentially expressed - silenced - in liver metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer, *DDX49*, *DDX56* and *DDX39A*.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the liver, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the liver to discover and describe a genes associated with the liver metastasis transcriptome in colorectal cancer.

Results

Figure 1: DDX49, DDX56 and DDX39A are differentially expressed in liver metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer.

I. Liver metastasis and primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer.

n=4 primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer

n=3 liver metastases from humans with colorectal cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
54555	2.65E-02	0.411	2.218795	0.9127169	876.27	DDX49	2691/19486	86.2
54606	4.76E-02	0.387	1.9807672	0.7666645	1814.02	DDX56	3432/19486	82.4
10212	1.75E-02	0.56	2.3770749	1.331301	2308.6	DDX39A	2252/19486	88.4

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the colorectum and in liver metastases of humans with colorectal cancer, we discovered differential expression of endothelial cell adhesion molecule, encoded by *DDX49*, *DDX56* and *DDX39A* in metastasis to the liver in humans with colorectal cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of DDX49, DDX56 and DDX39A changed more than 85%, 80%, and 85% of the human colorectal cancer (CRC) liver metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,486 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the positive fold-change indicating decreased quantity of DDX49, DDX56 and DDX39A messenger RNA in CRC liver metastases, demonstrating down-regulation of DDX49, DDX56 and DDX39A during disease progression in colorectal cancer.

II. Liver metastasis in patients with colorectal cancer.

n=10 primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer

n=10 liver metastases from humans with colorectal cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
54555	1.68E-03	0.206	3.1412252	0.64778222	53.34	DDX49	553/15341	96.4
10212	1.23E-02	0.29	2.5042384	0.72516483	108.28	DDX39A	1438/15341	90.6
54606	3.30E-02	0.167	2.1324954	0.35524186	149.8	DDX56	2320/15341	84.9

Through measurement of total transcription in the liver metastases of humans with colorectal cancer as compared to primary tumors of the colon and rectum, we validated differential expression of DDX49, DDX56 and DDX39A in human colorectal cancer (**Chart 2**). The expression of DDX49, DDX56 and DDX39A here changed more than 95%, 90% and nearly 85% of the liver metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 15,341 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the positive fold-change indicating decreased quantity of DDX49, DDX56 and DDX39A messenger

1 RNA in liver metastases, demonstrating down-regulation of DDX49, DDX56 and DDX39A during disease
2 progression and metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer.

3 Thus, differential and decreased expression of DDX49, DDX56 and DDX39A defines the liver
4 metastatic transcriptome in human colorectal cancer.

5 **Discussion**

6 We described here a set of genes from the DEAD-box (DDX) helicase that are differentially
7 expressed - silenced - in liver metastasis in humans with colorectal cancer, *DDX49*, *DDX56* and *DDX39A*.

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Methods

We utilized GSE213402 and GSE179979 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the liver and in primary tumors from humans with colorectal cancer using RNA-sequencing data (public and published) and R-based computational methods.